

Determination of methoxy group in the C-ring of a flavone using ^1H NMR

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Abstract : When ^1H NMR of a 3-methoxyflavone is compared with its 3-demethoxyflavone, H-2' and H-6' are found to be downfield in the former. This general observation is helpful for structural studies in naturally occurring flavones. The two flavones under comparison must have the same substituents in the B-rings; and different substituents in the A-rings do not change this observed trend.

Keywords : 3-Methoxyflavone, 3-demethoxyflavone, ^1H NMR, change in chemical shift, structural studies.

Introduction

Flavones are known to have several medicinal values¹: 3,5,7,8,3',4'-hexahydroxyflavone is used as an analgesic; apigenin 7,4'-dimethyl ether, naringenin and 5,7,3',4'-tetrahydroxyflavone 8-O-glucoside are known for anti-ulcer activity; 5,3',4'-trihydroxy-6-methoxyflavone has anti-inflammatory action; quercetin possesses antiviral activity; and flavonoids have been shown to inhibit some aspects of platelet function.

A general procedure² for locating OMe in naturally occurring flavones has already been described. The present paper deals with a procedure for locating 3-OMe; and it will enable in making a distinction amongst 5,6,7,8-, 3,5,6,7- and 3,5,7,8-tetramethoxyflavones; all these depict a singlet for one proton in ^1H NMR. It has also been shown earlier³ that chemical shift of a lone aromatic proton of the A-ring helps in differentiating between 5,6,7- and 5,7,8-trimethoxyflavones.

A comparison of ^1H NMR of 5-acetoxy-3,7,8,3',4'-pentamethoxyflavone (**3**⁴, δ 7.78, H-2'; δ 7.85, H-6') with that of 5-acetoxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (**4**⁵, δ 7.45, H-2'; δ 7.59, H-6') shows that H-2' and H-6' are downfield in the former. Change in chemical shifts (**3-4**) are: $\Delta\text{H-2}' = 0.33$ (7.78-7.45) and $\Delta\text{H-6}' = 0.26$ (7.85-7.59). Chemical shifts (δ) have been reported in Table 1, and change in chemical shifts (ΔH) have been placed in Table 2. There are similar trends for the comparisons **11-14**, **13-16**, **18-19** and **21-23**. These shifts have been termed as 3-methoxylation shifts.

Table 1. ^1H NMR literature data (δ , CDCl_3) for H-3, H-2' and H-6' in flavones

Positions of		Compd.	H-3	H-2'	H-6'
OAc	OMe				
-	3,5,6,7,4'	1 ⁴	-	8.07	8.07
5	3,6,7,3',4',5'	2 ⁴	-	7.33	7.33
5	3,7,8,3',4'	3 ⁴	-	7.78	7.85
5	7,8,3',4'	4 ⁵	6.56	7.45	7.59
5,3',4'	3,6,7	5 ⁴	-	7.93	8.00
5,3',4'	3,7,8	6 ⁶	-	8.10	8.11
5,4'	3,6,7	7 ⁴	-	8.06	8.06
5,4'	3,7,8	8 ⁴	-	8.24	8.24
5,6,4'	7	9 ⁷	6.58	7.90	7.90
5,7	3,6,4'	10 ⁸	-	8.04	8.04
5,7	3,8,3',4'	11 ⁴	-	7.95	8.02
5,7	3,8,3',4',5'	12 ⁹	-	7.43	7.43
5,7	3,8,4'	13 ⁹	-	8.08	8.08
5,7	8,3',4'	14 ¹⁰	6.48	7.24	7.39
5,7	8,3',4',5'	15 ¹⁰	6.49	6.98	6.98
5,7	8,4'	16 ¹⁰	6.47	7.69	7.69
5,7,3',4'	-	17 ¹⁰	6.56	7.28	7.46
5,7,3',4'	3,8	18 ⁶	-	8.03	8.05
5,7,3',4'	8	19 ¹⁰	6.49	7.62	7.62
5,7,4'	3,6,3'	20 ¹¹	-	7.78	7.70
5,7,4'	3,8,3'	21 ⁹	-	7.79	7.74
5,7,4'	8	22 ¹⁰	6.51	7.76	7.76
5,7,4'	8,3'	23 ¹⁰	6.51	7.30	7.36
5,7,8	3',4'	24 ¹⁰	6.53	7.23	7.37
5,7,8	4'	25 ¹⁰	6.54	7.70	7.70
5,7,8,4'	-	26 ¹⁰	6.55	7.73	7.73

Table-1 (contd.)

5,8,3',4'	7	27 ¹⁰	6.54	7.62	7.62
6,7	3',4',5'	28 ¹⁰	6.70	7.10	7.10
7	3,5,8,3',4'	29 ⁹	-	7.77	7.83
7	3,5,8,3',4',5'	30 ⁹	-	7.50	7.50
7	3,5,8,4'	31 ⁹	-	8.10	8.10
7,3',4'	3,5,8	32 ⁹	-	8.03	8.03

$$3-4 : \Delta H-2' = 0.33; \quad \Delta H-6' = 0.26$$

Table 2. ¹H NMR 3-methoxylation shifts (ΔH)^a in flavones

Comparisons	$\Delta H-2'$	$\Delta H-6'$	Comparisons	$\Delta H-2'$	$\Delta H-6'$
1-16 ^b	0.38	0.38	1-25 ^b	0.37	0.37
2-15 ^b	0.35	0.35	2-28 ^b	0.23	0.23
3-4 ^c	0.33	0.26	3-14 ^b	0.54	0.46
3-24 ^b	0.55	0.48	5-17 ^b	0.65	0.54
5-19 ^b	0.31	0.38	5-27 ^b	0.31	0.38
6-17 ^b	0.82	0.65	6-19 ^b	0.48	0.49
6-27 ^b	0.48	0.49	7-9 ^b	0.16	0.16
7-22 ^b	0.30	0.30	7-26 ^b	0.33	0.33
8-9 ^b	0.34	0.34	8-22 ^b	0.48	0.48
8-26 ^b	0.61	0.61	10-16 ^b	0.35	0.35
10-25 ^b	0.34	0.34	11-4 ^b	0.50	0.47
11-14 ^c	0.71	0.62	11-24 ^b	0.72	0.65
12-15 ^b	0.45	0.45	12-28 ^b	0.33	0.33
13-16 ^c	0.39	0.39	13-25 ^b	0.38	0.38
18-17 ^b	0.75	0.59	18-19 ^c	0.41	0.43
18-27 ^b	0.41	0.43	20-23 ^b	0.48	0.34
21-23 ^c	0.49	0.38	29-4 ^b	0.24	0.24
29-14 ^b	0.53	0.44	29-24 ^b	0.54	0.46
30-15 ^b	0.52	0.52	30-28 ^b	0.40	0.40
31-16 ^b	0.41	0.41	31-25 ^b	0.40	0.40
32-17 ^b	0.75	0.62	32-19 ^b	0.41	0.41
32-27 ^b	0.41	0.46			

^a $\Delta H = \delta$ value of the proton in 3-methoxyflavone minus that in 3-demethoxyflavone.

^bTwo flavones under comparison have different A-rings and identical B-rings.

^cTwo flavones under comparison have identical A- and B-rings.

It is shown hereunder that different substituents in the A-rings do not change this trend for the two compounds under comparison. The necessary condition is that the two compounds must have the same substituent in the B-ring; one has 3-methoxy and another is unsubstituted at C-3. The ¹H NMR of 3,5,6,7,4'-pentamethoxyflavone (1) and 5,7-diacetoxy-8,4'-dimethoxyflavone (16) shows that $\Delta H-2',6' = 0.38$ (Tables 1 and 2). Thirty nine other comparisons lend support to this observation.

$$1-16 : \Delta H-2',6' = 0.38$$

(A-ring substituents do not change the expected trend for 3-methoxylation shifts in flavones)

There is a report of natural occurrence of 3,5,6,8,3',4',5'-heptamethoxyflavone (33)¹²; and at a later stage it has been shown to be 3,5,7,8,3',4',5'-heptamethoxyflavone (34)¹³ which is already a known compound¹⁴. The change in chemical shift from 34 and 5,7-diacetoxy-8,3',4',5'-tetramethoxyflavone (15, Table 1) are 34-15: $\Delta H-2',6' = 0.59$, which are in order.

The range² (δ , CDCl₃) for H-6 in 5,7,8-trimethoxyflavones is 6.30–6.50; that for H-8 in 5,6,7-trimethoxyflavones is 6.67–6.80; and the range for H-3 is 6.48–6.70 (Table 1). It is evident that the range for H-3 overlaps with those of H-6 and H-8. The proposed procedure, coupled with these ranges, is helpful in making a distinction amongst 5,6,7,8-, 3,5,6,7- and 3,5,7,8-tetramethoxyflavones.

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